

Pacific oyster production (*Magallana gigas*) in Scotland (2015–2024): a descriptive analysis of the annual series

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Abstract

This study provides a descriptive analysis of Pacific oyster (*Magallana gigas*) production in Scotland over the period 2015–2024. Official data from the *Scottish Shellfish Farm Production Survey* were used, with production measured exclusively as the number of shells across the *Scottish Marine Regions*. The analysis was limited to physical production volumes and had a purely descriptive design.

Over the study period, total Scottish Pacific oyster production amounted to 37,803,000 specimens. The series reached a peak in 2017 (5,034,000 units) and a minimum in 2024 (2,418,000 shells), showing no linear growth pattern. After an initial increase up to 2017, production declined in 2018, recovered in 2019, contracted sharply in 2020, rose again in 2021, and then entered a new downward phase during 2022–2024. Territorial concentration was marked throughout the series. Over the decade, *Argyll* accounted for 47.1% of cumulative national production and *West Highlands & North Coast* for 38.7%, together representing more than 85% of the total. In 2024, *Argyll* alone accounted for 61.0% of national production, while *West Highlands & North Coast* showed the sharpest annual decline.

Introduction

The Pacific oyster (*Magallana gigas*) is one of the most important bivalves in contemporary aquaculture, representing a major component of global farmed mollusc production (Botta et al., 2020). However, the historical name *Crassostrea gigas* remains widely used in both the literature and industry practice. In 2017, the separation of Pacific oysters from the genus *Crassostrea* and their transfer to the genus *Magallana* were proposed on the basis of a molecular systematics study grounded in phylogenetic analyses of mitochondrial and nuclear markers (Salvi and Mariottini, 2017). Nevertheless, the *World Register of Marine Species* still lists *Crassostrea gigas* as an accepted alternate representation of *Magallana gigas* (WoRMS Editorial Board, n.d.). In production and commercial datasets, the same species may also appear under the names *Pacific oyster* or

Pacific cupped oyster. These terms do not identify different biological entities, but simply represent terminological variants referring to the same Pacific oyster.

A typically coastal-estuarine species, the Pacific oyster (*Magallana gigas*) readily colonises hard substrates and is able to tolerate wide environmental variability (Troost, 2010; FAO, n.d.). According to the FAO species profile, gametogenesis begins at around 10 °C within a salinity range of 15 to 32‰, whereas spawning is generally associated with water temperatures above 20 °C (FAO, n.d.). After fertilisation, larvae remain suspended in the water column for several weeks before settling on the substrate (Troost, 2010). Experimental studies have also shown that larval survival may remain high even at temperatures below those considered optimal, although effects on growth and metamorphosis are still observed (Ben Kheder et al., 2010; Rico-Villa et al., 2009).

In the United Kingdom, marketable Pacific oysters (*Magallana gigas*) are generally associated with a shell-on live weight of approximately 75 g (Seafish, 2005). More broadly, commercial size ranges of approximately 70 to 100 g shell-on have been reported for the species (FAO, n.d.). In the British live oyster trade, however, market grades may extend from about 35–40 g up to around 100 g per specimen, reflecting grading practices that are not always species-specific (Stroud, n.d.).

The economic importance of the species is equally evident. According to Eurostat, in 2023 production of *Pacific cupped oyster* within the European Union was heavily concentrated in France, which accounted for approximately 89% of the total. At the global scale, *cupped oysters* accounted for about 33% of total mollusc production in 2022 (Eurostat, 2024). The species also occupies a prominent position in the Scottish context: the official *Scottish Shellfish Farm Production Survey 2024* reports that shellfish production was dominated mainly by *common mussel* and *Pacific oyster* (Scottish Government, 2025).

Against this background, a descriptive reading of the Scottish series for 2015–2024 is useful for defining the size of the sector, its interannual variability, and the relative weight of the production areas. The aim of the present study is to describe the annual pattern of Pacific oyster production across the *Scottish Marine Regions*, using exclusively the number of specimens as the primary measure of output.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective descriptive study was conducted using official data from the Scottish Shellfish Farm Production Survey, with specific reference to the resource *2024 Statistics: Pacific Oyster Production and Value by Scottish Marine Regions*, published by the Scottish Government, Marine Directorate as part of the official survey dataset. The resource states that production is reported in numbers of shells and that the data include both the individual Scottish Marine Regions and the national total, *All Scotland* (Scottish Government, Marine Directorate, 2025a; Scottish Government, Marine Directorate, 2025b). The overall dataset is described as an annual compilation of production and employment statistics for Scottish shellfish farming. The associated methodological documentation further specifies that the data are derived from responses to an annual questionnaire sent to all licensed and active Scottish shellfish farming enterprises (Scottish Government, Marine Directorate, 2025a; Scottish Government, 2025).

In the present study, only the production variable expressed as shell numbers was considered. Monetary information was excluded, as the analysis was intended solely to describe the physical volumes of production. Six territorial units were examined: Argyll, Clyde, Orkney Islands & Shetland Isles, Outer Hebrides, West Highlands & North Coast, and the national total, *All Scotland*. Before interpretation of the results, the arithmetic consistency of the series was verified by checking, for each year, whether the sum of the five regional values matched the national total expressed in numbers of shells. The analysis remained exclusively descriptive, with no inferential models applied.

Results

Over the period 2015–2024, total Scottish Pacific oyster production amounted to 37,803,000 specimens. The series reached its maximum in 2017, with 5,034,000 units, whereas the minimum was recorded in 2024, with 2,418,000 shells.

The temporal pattern does not show linear growth (Figure 1). After an initial increase between 2015 and 2017, production declined in 2018, recovered in 2019, underwent a marked contraction in 2020, rose again in 2021, and then entered a new downward phase during the three-year period 2022–2024. The final value recorded in 2024 was 10.2% lower than in 2015 and 52.0% lower than the 2017 peak.

From a territorial perspective, the series was supported almost entirely by *Argyll* and *West Highlands & North Coast* (Figure 2). Over the decade, *Argyll* accounted for 17,823,000 shells, corresponding to 47.1% of the cumulative national total, whereas *West Highlands & North Coast* contributed 14,616,000 specimens, equivalent to 38.7%. The other areas accounted for a much smaller share: *Clyde* represented 7.3% of the total, *Outer Hebrides* 5.9%, and *Orkney Islands & Shetland Isles* 1.0%.

In 2024, the territorial distribution changed markedly (Figure 2). *Argyll* accounted for 61.0% of the Scottish total, whereas *West Highlands & North Coast* fell to 13.0%, approaching *Clyde* (12.3%). In the same year, *Orkney Islands & Shetland Isles* and *Outer Hebrides* contributed 7.1% and 6.7%, respectively. The sharpest decline was observed in *West Highlands & North Coast*, which fell from 1,745,000 shells in 2023 to 314,000 in 2024 (–82%).

Figure 1. Total annual production of Pacific oyster in Scotland, expressed as number of shells, over the period 2015–2024.

Figure 2. Annual number of shells harvested across the five production areas of Scotland. Production was dominated mainly by Argyll and West Highlands & North Coast; from 2023 onward, output was supported largely by Argyll alone.

Discussion

The picture that emerges is that of a small and highly concentrated production sector. Two areas alone, *Argyll* and *West Highlands & North Coast*, account for more than 85% of the cumulative production recorded over the decade. A system with this structure is inevitably vulnerable to local imbalances. If even one of the two main areas slows down, the national total is affected immediately and visibly.

The 2024 figure also requires particular caution in interpretation. The official *Scottish Shellfish Farm Production Survey 2024* reports that *Pacific oyster* production declined by 38% and links this decrease to the cessation of activity of a major producer in the *Highland region* during the same year (Scottish Government, 2025). Consequently, the sharp downturn at the end of the series should not be interpreted simply as a biological, climatic, or market-driven effect. Part of the decline

instead appears compatible with a structural business-related event. Since the administrative report uses the term *Highland region*, whereas the analytical table is organised by *Scottish Marine Regions*, a cautious formulation is advisable, and the two geographies should not be rigidly conflated.

From a biological perspective, the marked interannual variability of the species is not surprising. *Magallana gigas* is a bivalve whose reproductive maturation, spawning, and larval survival depend to a considerable extent on thermal and salinity conditions (Troost, 2010; FAO, n.d.). However, the series analysed here does not allow the contribution of environmental factors to be distinguished from that of business decisions, seed availability, production continuity at farming sites, or the continued presence of operators in the market. These data describe production trends effectively, but on their own they are not sufficient to explain the deeper causes of the observed fluctuations.

Conclusions

Between 2015 and 2024, Scottish Pacific oyster production showed a markedly fluctuating pattern, with a peak in 2017 and a low point in 2024. The entire series was dominated by *Argyll* and *West Highlands & North Coast*, confirming a strongly concentrated territorial structure. This concentration makes the national total particularly sensitive to local disturbances and to specific business-related events.

The decline observed in 2024 should therefore not be interpreted as a simple linear downturn of the sector, but rather considered in light of the cessation of activity of a major producer, as reported by the official source. Overall, the series documents not so much a regular trajectory of growth or decline as a highly variable, concentrated, and vulnerable production system in which the ecology of the species and the business structure appear to be closely intertwined.

Author Contribution

The author conceived the study, carried out the data analysis, and wrote the manuscript. GPT-based tools (ChatGPT, OpenAI) were used for exploratory activities, formal improvement of the bibliography, statistical checking, and translation of the manuscript into English.

Data Availability

The data analysed in the present study are available in the attached file: *2024 Pacific_oyster_production_and_value_2013-2024_by_SMR.xlsx*.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest.

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